

SPACE AND TERRESTRIAL COMMUNICATIONS
IN MILITARY CRISIS RESPONSE

by

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Traditionally in a peacetime environment, military communicators train and plan for war. In so doing, we address the full spectrum of conflict--low, mid, and high intensity warfare. That focus on training is correct given the understanding that the greatest danger to our Nation's security is the traditional concept of war. Since Vietnam, our Nation has not been at war; however, military forces have been deployed around the world protecting our national interests. The communications required to support those operations have been complex, provided on short notice, and essential not only to the success of military operations, but also in carrying out our Government's policies protecting our national interests and our citizens. During the past few years, operations against Libya, in the Persian Gulf, and in Central America are but a few examples of the types of crisis or contingency operations demanding extraordinary planning and effort on the part of military communicators. Such efforts may again be required in the future.

Before discussing space and terrestrial communications in military response to crises, it is necessary to understand the environment in which communications planners must operate, an environment full of unknowns. The geographic location of the next crisis is virtually unpredictable. The sophistication, reliability, and availability of existing commercial communications systems in most areas susceptible to crises is questionable at best. Military organizations tasked to respond to a crisis are seldom identified until hours or at most days before deployment. In looking back over the past few crises, forces were usually joint, i.e., consisting of two or more services. Invariably there were questions and issues about both their internal communications and interoperability capabilities. Distances covered by communications are often great, not necessarily in the area of operations, but in links back to the Commanders-in-Chief (CINC's) and National Command Authorities. Timing for installation of communications is usually critical for crisis response with a typical required "comm-up date" being "yesterday." Given this challenging environment and not knowing the answers to "where?, when?, or who?", current and future communications planners must address three areas: tactical connectivity, Defense Communications System (DCS) connectivity, and commercial communications. Let's examine space and terrestrial capabilities for all three areas in the present and mid term.

SPACE SYSTEMS IN CRISIS RESPONSE: Military Satellite Systems are, and will continue to be, the backbone of crisis communications, especially for long-distance requirements. A difficult problem to resolve during crises is that of capacity, whereby existing operational circuits on satellites are often subject to preemption or rerouting. We should not think of our satellite constellations as "pure" command and control communications systems because other users often depend on the same satellites. The age and capacity (or lack thereof) of some of the satellites causes competition between various communities for both existing capabilities and future launches. This is mentioned only to emphasize that we do not

have at present, nor will we have in the immediate future, the ability to allow unrestricted access to any military satellite for all potential users.

UHF military satellite communications (MILSATCOM) operate over the Fleet Satellite (FLTSAT/AFSAT/LEASAT) constellations and provide the communications backbone during crises. Availability, transportability, reliability, and ease of operating UHF tactical satellite (TACSAT) terminals make them ideal for getting communications on site quickly. However, user requirements now exceed available capacity. Over-reliance on scarce MILSATCOM resources often occurs during planning in crisis situations. Thus we need to take advantage of 5KHZ tunable terminals to alleviate capacity problems for secure voice such as Advanced Narrow Band Digital Voice Terminal (ANDVT) and comparable equipment. Likewise, we need to expand the use of Demand Assigned Multiple Access (DAMA) and similar systems to increase capacity and efficiency of 25KHZ channels on the FLTSATS. Whatever we can develop to increase the efficiency of existing capabilities will be welcome. Launch problems, limitations on the military UHF frequency band, and financial constraints all dictate that we make the most out of what we have.

Another potential problem in satellite communications for the crisis planner is jamming. We have been fortunate in not experiencing intentional jamming of the UHF constellations during actual missions, but the potential for such is high. UHF satellites are highly susceptible to jamming and to potential enemy attack. The communications planner, therefore, must avoid total reliance on this non-survivable communications medium.

SHF MILSATCOM, traditionally operating over DCS II and III, is usually the mainstay for the consolidation phase of crisis operations. It provides long distance multichannel communications for tactical users. Because of size and weight constraints--terminals tend to be large and heavy--transportability is a major planning consideration. Although SHF access during a crisis is not as great a problem as in the UHF spectrum, these satellites are also at capacity for conventional planning purposes. Crisis communications planners must coordinate closely with the Defense Communications Agency--the system manager--with regard to DCS entry and the Army for ground mobile force (GMF) satellite access.

In the future, EHF communications over systems such as Milstar, will undoubtedly play a role in crisis response. Whatever that role, Milstar will not replace UHF or SHF systems currently in use. This is because of size and transportability of the equipment, and pointing accuracy of antennas. Although many potential uses are yet to be explored, Milstar is not likely to be a panacea for current capacity problems.

Military satellite communications will not be sufficient unto themselves in future crises. We must take advantage of commercial satellite systems for several reasons. The first reason is the capacity problem already mentioned. Second is the need to

communicate with friendly governments, or in the most recent case in the Persian Gulf, with commercial shipping. Installation of military terminal equipment and its associated cryptologic gear is often prohibited or impractical. Commercial satellite radios, Data Encryption Standard (DES) equivalent crypto systems, and leased channels can fill this void.

TERRESTRIAL SYSTEMS IN CRISIS RESPONSE: Services provided by the Defense Communications System in a peacetime environment (voice, message, and data) are all required during times of crisis. It is necessary then to interface the tactical military equipment at the crisis location to the DCS entry stations scattered worldwide. Indeed, DCS interface for HF, UHF, and SHF is vital in crisis response, not only from the standpoint of service from switched systems, e.g., AUTODIN and AUTOVON, but also from that of preserving satellite capacity.

As previously mentioned, the nature of crisis communications response is joint. Terrestrial communications assets used to support crisis situations are predominantly controlled by the Joint Chiefs of Staff (JCS) or a CINC. The Joint Communications Support Element (JCSE) at MacDill Air Force Base, Florida, is the largest military communications unit dedicated to crisis response. Equipment deployments can be tailored to meet specific requirements from single items of equipment to large-scale packages capable of meeting the entire communications needs of a joint task force (JTF) or special operations joint task force. Modernization of the JCSE is an ongoing process. The active duty JCSE organization will possess state-of-the-art terminal and transmission systems to provide local and long-haul communications for two separate headquarters. Two additional separate headquarters can be equipped from the Air National Guard's 290th and 224th Joint Communications Support Squadrons. Other JCS-controlled communications equipment is operated and maintained by the Services and is likewise in the process of being upgraded.

The possibility of multiple crises occurring simultaneously is real and requires additional terrestrial assets be available to CINCs in their own areas of operation. For the past several years, those needs have been addressed through expenditures of "CINC Initiative Funds" specifically earmarked for near term communications improvements. In the past, emphasis has been primarily on purchasing transportable UHF satellite terminals. However, other types of equipment are now being purchased also. When CINC component commands possess substantial communications capabilities, planning is needed to develop their own JTF communications packages in the event JCS-controlled assets are unavailable.

The size and amount of terrestrial communications equipment required to adequately support a JTF is of concern. In a fast-breaking crisis, airlift of such equipment is a large requirement and can compete with operational ground forces for transport assets. We must continue to down-size our communications equipment. If the force involved in crisis response is large, we can anticipate delays in communications deployment because of competition for limited numbers of aircraft.

To this point discussion has focused on military terrestrial systems. In many cases the solutions to crisis communications requirements are more readily found in the civilian commercial sector. Over the

past few years significant progress has been made in producing communications hardware suitable for military use over commercial media. Examples include Secure Telephone Units II and III, laptop or suitcase size computers, facsimile machines, and various crypto systems. The ability to provide secure communications for voice, message, and data over commercial paths using small, lightweight equipment is the way of the future. The more adaptable such equipment is to the peculiarities of various national and international telecommunications systems, the better it will be for the military.

In conclusion, communications for crisis response will depend upon a mix of space and terrestrial systems from both military and civilian sectors. Our current capabilities are good and will be improved in the immediate future. In the near term we must continue to take steps to maximize our existing satellite capacity, find ways to make our long-haul equipment lighter and more transportable, and invest in commercial communications equipment which can provide secure paths over international systems. The technology to accomplish these tasks is here or on the immediate horizon. Accomplishing them in a timely and cost effective manner will be our real challenge.